

Report on Stakeholders Engagement

D2.2

Document information Summary

Date	30 September 2018
Document title	D2.2 Report on Stakeholders Engagement
Leader Partner	INGV
Main Author(s)	Carmela Freda, Giovanna Maracchia, Massimo Cocco
Contributing author(s)	-
Reviewer(s)	Laura Platt, Marialetizia Mari, Stanka Šebela
Approved by	PMO
Target audiences	Project partners, EC
Keywords	EPOS; Communication; Engagement; Stakeholders
Deliverable nature	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Delivery date	M36 (Official)
Version/Date	5/26 September 2018

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY 3

1. STAKEHOLDERS' CATEGORIES..... 4

2. STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT..... 7

 2.1 Stakeholder Category: Scientists..... 7

 2.1.1 Data Providers within the solid Earth community 7

 2.1.2 Data users within the solid Earth community..... 7

 2.1.3 Data users outside the solid Earth community..... 8

 2.1.4 IT experts..... 8

 2.2 Stakeholder Category: Governments..... 9

 2.2.1 National Governments 9

 2.2.2 Funding Agencies (including Civil Protection Agencies)..... 10

 2.2.3 European Commission..... 10

 2.3 Stakeholder Category: Private Sector..... 11

 2.4 Stakeholder Category: Society 11

ANNEX 1 - EPOS INFO-DAY LJUBLJANA..... 13

ANNEX 2 – REPORT ON CONSULTATION WITH PRIVATE SECTOR..... 16

Executive summary

The first version of this document, currently stored in the EPOS Intranet, has been drafted as an internal report on Month 12 (September 2016) to describe the EPOS stakeholder's engagement activities performed during the first year of the EPOS IP project.

Deliverable 2.2 intends to recall the strategy adopted by EPOS to engage stakeholders as well as on the related engagement activities after three years from the starting of the project.

In accordance with its scientific vision of creating a pan-European infrastructure to support solid Earth research, the EPOS mission is to integrate the diverse and advanced European Research Infrastructures for solid Earth science, relying on new e-science opportunities. In this context, to reach the goal of having maximum exploitation in terms of both large volume of used services and a large number of users, "engagement" means the active participation and direct contribution of very diverse stakeholders to the initiative. Referring to EPOS, diverse stakeholder categories mean the solid Earth scientists, but also scientists belonging to disciplines outside the solid Earth domain, decision-makers, private sector and, critically, society.

The action of engaging requires effective dissemination and communication toward target audiences aimed at fostering their involvement to the EPOS enterprise. Generally speaking, workshops, meetings, teleconferences, written documents are the most effective tools for interacting with stakeholders that are already involved in EPOS, e.g., scientists within the solid Earth domains, IT experts, governments. The latter stakeholders' categories continuously need to be maintained informed and involved. Brokerage events and dedicated tools such as web, social media, reports promotional and dissemination material targeted to each different audience are the best way to succeed in inspiring and eventually engaging potential stakeholders, e.g., data users within and outside the solid Earth domain, private sector, society.

In the first chapter, we define the diverse stakeholders' categories critical for EPOS and the adopted interaction timeline. Then, we detail the main activities performed from M1 (October 2015) to M36 (September 2018) to efficiently engage these stakeholders, following the directives illustrated in the EPOS Communication Plan (D2.1).

1. Stakeholders' Categories

During the Preparatory Phase, EPOS needed to aggregate and strengthen the very diverse scientific communities belonging to the solid Earth science to ensure their availability in providing data and data products for the integration plan; IT experts were also involved since the beginning to contribute to the EPOS activities; at the same time, it was clear that the involvement of national governments (i.e., the bodies that guarantee the sustainability of the national research infrastructures in charge of providing data) was vital for the success of the initiative. Therefore, the primary “communication” goal of the Preparatory Phase was to inform, collaborate, and engage these specific stakeholder categories, namely data providers, IT experts and governments. The approach EPOS had with other categories, e.g., data users, the private sector, and the society, was necessarily more focused on merely informing them about the EPOS vision and mission.

In the current Implementation Phase, EPOS has slightly revised the stakeholders' classification by disaggregating the categories into target audiences (Table 1). This has been pondered necessary for adequately addressing the new challenges of integrating and make accessible data and products and for involving further stakeholders such as the private sector and society.

Table 1. Stakeholder's categories and target audiences in EPOS Implementation Phase

	Stakeholder's Categories	Target Audiences
I	Scientists	Data providers
		Data users within the solid Earth community
		Data users outside the solid Earth community
		IT experts
II	Governments	National Governments
		Funding Agencies (including Civil Protection agencies)
		European Commission
III	Private Sector	Large Industry
		Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs)
IV	Society	Students at any level
		General public

Nonetheless, efficient communication with such diverse communities requires not only to focus messages on tightly defined audiences but also to timely interact by balancing between the readiness of the EPOS offer and the stakeholder interest. For this purpose, EPOS, already in the Preparatory Phase with an update in the current Implementation Phase, surveyed the interest of different stakeholders within the initiative as well as the influence they might have on it (Figure 1). All identified target audiences have been analysed considering the interest they might have in the EPOS integration plan and the influence they have in controlling the legal structure governing its construction and maintenance. Both, interest and influence of each audience can be described as somewhere between passive and active:

- the **interest** is active when the stakeholder contributes to the ICS & TCS construction and maintenance while is passive when the stakeholder is mostly an end-user of the EPOS provision;
- the **influence** is active when the stakeholder is authoritative and therefore capable of influencing the EPOS governance and decisions; on the contrary, the power is passive when the stakeholder is mostly influenced by EPOS decisions.

By mapping the variable levels of interest and influence across the diverse stakeholders, we could adapt communication actions to the specific needs of each target audience by identifying for each communication activity the specific purpose and contents, the phase, the mode and timeline and person/body in charge. In particular, in Figure 1, the phase indicates the evolution stage of the communication action (Inform → Consult → Collaborate → Engage → Approve). In Figure 1, the different areas of the diagram identify the current phase in the stakeholder interaction (inform, consult, collaborate, engage),

Figure 1. Level of interest and influence across the diverse EPOS stakeholders surveyed during the Implementation Phase. Colours identify the different target audiences to match the stakeholders' categories following the code as in Table 1: orange-scientists, yellow-governments, green-private sector, purple-society. Training and educational institutions/initiatives have two colours because they involve both scientists and the general public. Data providers, national governments and funding agencies, and IT experts have and will continue to have a high active influence and interest in EPOS. Activities have been planned to further interact and communicate with the private sector and the society (general public). Training activities and engagement of universities and academies are starting in EPOS IP to ensure the full exploitation of results.

This exercise of mapping the interest vs influence of stakeholders also allowed to define the timeline for effective interaction with them. The first version of this timeline has been released at M6 in the EPOS communication Plan (D2.1), here we present the version updated during the first three years of the project (Figure 2). Once the interaction between EPOS and the stakeholders is initiated, it generally continues for the whole project time-life. For example, concerted efforts to engage with the scientific community took place already in the EPOS Conception and Preparatory Phases (2006-2014). With a consolidated community now intact, engagement is continuing during the whole EPOS Implementation Phase and beyond. The stakeholder's category Governments has been informed during the Conception Phase, and the engagement has been consolidated during the Preparatory Phase and is now continuing in the Implementation Phase. In particular, interactions with several national Civil Protection Agencies have started demonstrating their interest in the EPOS infrastructure. Moreover, several communities involved in EPOS are also participating to service provision toward the European Civil Defence through the ARISTOTELE initiative. EPOS is also contributing to the EC Community of Users initiatives to implement the provision of effective information to society in an ethical coherent way. The "Private Sector" has been only informed about the EPOS initiative during the Preparatory Phase. In the current Implementation Phase, EPOS launched a consultation activity within the Thematic Core Services with the aim of mapping the landscape of interactions with the private sector within the EPOS communities. The goal was to assess the impact of such interactions on EPOS data and service provision and to plan future engagement strategies. Regarding "Society", a bi-lateral form of interaction has not been started yet. We are convinced that to capture the society interest (meaning students and the general public, as for the EPOS target audiences), the EPOS provision, if not fully operative, must be at least partially implemented having clearly defined the services provided by the TCS and set up the ICS platform.

Figure 2. Stakeholder interaction timeline. Note: "Inform, Consult, Collaborate, Engage, Approve", represent subsequent evolution stages (phases) of the communication action (see paragraph 4.2 of D2.1 Communication Plan delivered at M6). Phases, as reported in this timeline, mean to indicate the highest-level reached for the corresponding category. For example, the "Inform" phase on the stakeholder category Society, means that EPOS has not started any bi-lateral form of communication with this category (Society has a passive influence and interest in EPOS, see Fig. 2).

2. Stakeholders Engagement

This chapter details the communication actions undertaken during the first three years of the EPOS IP project to engage stakeholders efficiently.

2.1 Stakeholder Category: Scientists

2.1.1 Data Providers within the solid Earth community

Data providers have been involved in EPOS since the Conception Phase to actively contribute to creating the conditions for its design and for the definition of its vision and mission of integrating national research infrastructures and international organizations. During the Preparatory Phase, data providers have been formally engaged through Working Groups, and their effective contribution has been recorded in the Research Infrastructure Database for EPOS (RIDE, <https://www.epos-ip.org/ride>). This was the pre-condition for envisaging the potentiality of the EPOS data and service provision and essential for designing the EPOS architecture. Moving from the Preparatory to the Implementation Phase corresponded in shifting from Working Groups, focused on aggregating each involved scientific community, to Thematic Core Services (TCS) whose goal is to represent the community and manage its governance. Thematic Core Services (TCS) involve data providers and the associated communities at different levels: from national research infrastructures, aware of the EPOS integration plan and fully supporting it by developing services (i.e., fully engaged), to contributing institutions that follow and contribute to the implementation plan (i.e., collaborating). The necessity to engage as many data providers and "TCS developers" as possible led to the partnership enlargement from EPOS Preparatory Phase to EPOS Implementation Phase from 20 to 47 beneficiaries.

EPOS IP continuously interacts with data providers remotely, via the EPOS Intranet, but also by organizing, twice a year, integration workshops attended by all key players (Prague, March 2016; Prague, March 2017; Bucharest, October 2017; Lisbon, March 2018; Barcelona, October 2018). These integration workshops, designed for sharing outcomes, plan activities, and tackle challenges, served to maintain all key players and communities interested and. Other communication tools used to interact with this target audience are the website, the social media and the newsletter.

2.1.2 Data users within the solid Earth community

Not all scientists belonging to the solid Earth community can be categorized as Data Providers. Indeed, a large portion of researchers are not directly involved in providing data, but are surely interested in using the EPOS data and services. These scientists are well aware of EPOS and of its provision because EPOS anyway, at national level, already involves research organizations not directly involved in the provision of data. Currently, EPOS involves nearly 140 research organizations from 25 countries, 64 out of these 138 are involved in delivering data and services, the remaining already represent potential users of the EPOS infrastructures. Nevertheless, users within solid Earth science need to be further engaged also in testing the quality and effectiveness of the services EPOS is offering.

The EPOS efforts to engage its user's community translate into dedicated initiatives such as regional conferences and brokerage events and dedicated dissemination and communication activities.

In particular, ZRC SAZU (Slovenia), in collaboration with IGF PAS (Poland), and INGV (Italy) organized an EPOS Brokerage event in Ljubljana (Slovenia) targeted to potential users and stakeholders from the Eastern Adriatic area. More details and the outcomes of the "EPOS Info-Day" are reported in the Annex 1 of this document.

Moreover, EPOS regularly attends the European Geoscience Union (EGU) General Assemblies organizing its own session where scientists are invited to present possible interaction at various levels and Splinter meetings dedicated to the community interactions. The EPOS booth at EGU is as well an opportunity for scientists to meet and discuss EPOS achievements. The engagement of the community is also ensured through the interactions with other European projects (e.g., MEDSUV, MARSITE, FUTUREVOLC, NEMOH, TOPOMOD, TSUMAPS, ARISTOTELE, SERA) as well as with international initiatives (e.g., TopoEurope, GEO, GEM, InterMagnet) and organizations (e.g., EuroGeoSurveys, EUREF).

The present challenge for EPOS is to move from a data provider-driven approach to a user-driven approach. The identification and communication of the data and service provision (Data, Products, Software, and Service – DDSS – elements) as well as the implementation of the Thematic and Integrated Core Services (TCS and ICS) will foster engagement of the user community within solid Earth science. Moreover, undertaking initiatives to implement training activities (also in synergy with Initial Training Networks ITN projects and ERC awarded fellowships) will be a complementary way to engage the solid Earth user community.

2.1.3 Data users outside the solid Earth community

Communication activities devoted to Users outside the solid Earth domain are still emergent and need to be implemented during the operational phase, after the EPOS provision has been tested. Presently, the EPOS strategy is to collaborate with other Environmental RIs being part of the ESFRI roadmap and participating to projects and global initiatives such as ENVRIplus (the cluster of Environmental RIs) and the Group on Earth Observations (GEO).

EPOS participation in the ENVRIPlus project and contribution to the Board of European Environmental RIs (BEERI) facilitates exchanging of experiences and solutions as well as sharing efforts for communication and dissemination activities. EPOS and ENVRIPlus have organized common initiatives during the European Geoscience Union (EGU) and the American Geophysical Union (AGU) conferences. The collaboration and communication with communities from the Marine and Atmospheric domains allow undertaking common initiatives to engage new user communities committed both to implement new infrastructures (sea bottom observations, tsunami data, bathymetry, etc.) and to use existing services across pre-defined boundaries and disciplines.

EPOS is a GEO participating organization and it is coordinating the development of the Geo-Hazard Supersites in Europe within the GEO framework. This has fostered communication and collaborations with the space agencies (European Space Agency (ESA), NASA, German, French and Italian space Agencies), which increased the knowledge concerning EPOS architecture and integration plan. Moreover, the European Supersites (Italian and Icelandic Volcanoes and the Marmara Sea Near Fault Observatory) presently under implementation and integration in EPOS have been proposed as candidate sites for cross-disciplinary researches engaging other communities outside solid Earth sciences (health for security and multi-hazard, environmental chemistry for pollution and contamination, technological innovation for new sensors and observing systems, etc.). This target audience will be further engaged during the last year of EPOS IP project.

2.1.4 IT experts

EPOS is also actively communicating with scientists belonging to e-sciences and ICT innovation (therefore being outside the solid Earth domain). This communication activity relies on the co-design approach adopted in EPOS since its preparatory phase (EPOS PP) and fostering the interaction with IT scientists to support the implementation of the EPOS IT architecture and service provision. To this goal, EPOS is participating in several IT projects such as EUDAT, EUDAT2020, EGI-Engage, RDA-Europe, VR4EIC and is contributing to European

and global initiatives such as OpenAire, EGI, RDA. This long-lasting communication and engagement of e-science initiatives and e-infrastructures have facilitated the EPOS inclusion in the European Open Science Cloud Pilot proposal (EOSC), which has the objective to design the governance and sustainability model to develop the European Cloud initiative and the EOSC-hub project as well as the European Data Infrastructure. EPOS has represented the ENVRI community in the 2017 EOSC stakeholder consultations on data science for environmental research infrastructures.

IT scientists have been engaged in EPOS since the beginning of the preparatory phase, and the present communication activities are dedicated to implementing procurement policies to provide access to computational resources (ICS-D) as well as to ensure data curation and preservation. Dissemination of EPOS functional architecture and IT prototype is essential for participating in the debates on the design of the EOSC and to the Federation of computational resources.

2.2 Stakeholder Category: Governments

2.2.1 National Governments

National Governments have been engaged in EPOS since the beginning of the Preparatory Phase (2010). Already during the conception of EPOS, it was very clear that infrastructure could not have advanced toward the implementation and operation without the involvement and significant contribution of the national governments. This was not meant as a mere financial contribution. Indeed, the successful establishment of the EPOS observing system and related services to users also requires to negotiate with countries both the legal and governance framework and the technical implementations. The latter is needed to achieve not only the accessibility of the data provided by the national research infrastructures but also the interconnectivity and interoperability of the available resources. For this reason, during the Preparatory Phase, the Inter-Activity Preparatory Council (IAPC) was established. This Council, composed of scientists representing each contracting partner (corresponding to the involved country in the preparatory phase) and one representative for each associate partner, had the duty of overseeing the EPOS progress toward construction as well as of motivating their respective governments to support the EPOS infrastructure. One of the first action of the IAPC has been to arrange funding agencies and government's representatives at an extraordinary meeting, inviting them to constitute the Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR). The first EPOS BGR meeting took place in Paris on November the 29th 2012, and it was attended by representatives of 17 out of the 23 countries participating to EPOS. The main objective of this first meeting was to allow the Board Members to understand what EPOS was aiming to build, by using which legal tools, and how much all this would have cost. Four more BGR meetings have been organized during the Preparatory Phase.

In the current Implementation Phase, 23 countries (over 25 participating in EPOS) have officially nominated through their research ministries (or equivalent), their own representative in the Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR). Since the beginning of the Implementation Phase six more meetings have been organised (eleven in total since the Preparatory Phase):

- Lisbon (Portugal), 31 March - 1 April 2016
- Vienna (Austria), 3 - 4 November 2016
- Warsaw (Poland), 23 - 24 February 2017
- Athens (Greece), 7 - 8 June 2017
- Berlin (Germany), 14 - 15 December 2017
- Bratislava (Slovak Republic), 21 - 22 May 2018

The last BGR meeting, before the first EPOS-ERIC General Assembly, will be held in November 2018, in Rome. All EPOS BGR meetings have always been attended by a large majority of Members. This allowed taking strategic decisions fundamental for the infrastructure being sure of having the agreement of all countries. Some examples of those pivotal decisions are: EPOS Architecture, selection of the ECO Hosting Country and the ICS-C Hosting Country, Financial Plan, TCS Cost-Book, Data Policy, Service Validation, Statutes (including the formula to calculate the membership fee).

2.2.2 Funding Agencies (including Civil Protection Agencies)

The present challenge is to further involve funding agencies in EPOS.

In particular, EPOS visibility and recognition from national Civil Protection agencies is increasing. Interactions with this target audience are now concerning the EPOS data and service provision. Civil protection agencies should be a key stakeholder with whom agree about the information and the services that EPOS will provide to society as well as to other stakeholders involved in geo-hazards assessment and risk mitigation. Moreover, the EPOS community is involved in using data and services generated by national research infrastructures and thematic core services for providing expert opinions and authoritative information to the European Civil Protection, as in the framework of the ARISTOTELE initiative.

Other funding agencies will be engaged in EPOS during the Testing and pre-Operational Phase. In particular, EPOS-ERIC will elaborate an engagement strategy shared with the communities to further contribute to its financial viability.

2.2.3 European Commission

This target audience has been, necessarily, engaged in EPOS since the beginning of the Preparatory Phase. Presently, the communication with the European Commission is not limited to the formal management and guidance of the EPOS IP project. EPOS is interacting with several distinct directorates of the European Commission, not limited to DG-Research. Indeed, EPOS is interacting with:

- DG-CONNECT for IT innovation and implementation;
- Societal Challenges for technological innovation, risk management and security of citizens;
- DG-ECHO for the services to National Civil Defence Agencies, testing the possibility to contribute to the European Alert system for natural hazards;
- DG-Space for contributing to Earth Observations and for implementing services to develop new products from satellite data.

During the Implementation phase, EPOS directly interacted with the European Commission (DG-RTD) in various meetings dedicated to the EPOS-ERIC legal establishment.

In the framework of the European Commission, ESFRI is, of course, an essential stakeholder for EPOS. When ESFRI and the European Commission proposed EPOS as a RIs of a global perspective, one important communication initiative been to host the 9th meeting of the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on the Global Research Infrastructures (May the 15th and 16th 2017, Naples Italy) together with European Marine Biological Research Center. The Group met with the goal of exploring collaboration opportunities of research infrastructure initiatives that have demonstrated a significant level of maturity towards becoming potential GRIs. The progress on the activities of the GSO has been reported to the G7 Science Ministers' meeting that took place in September 2017 in Torino, Italy.

2.3 Stakeholder Category: Private Sector

The Private Sector represents one of the EPOS stakeholders' categories (disaggregated into Large Industry and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises target audiences) that must be engaged in the light of an as wide as possible exploitation of the EPOS achievements. Effective engagement of the private sector would certainly contribute to demonstrate the economic impact of the infrastructure. However, cooperation with the private sector is a challenge for publicly funded RIs, such as EPOS that must retain impartiality and public-good role. Moreover, cooperation with the private sector must manage in parallel with scientific, financial, legal, governance, and ethics issues. The latter is especially pertinent for environmental RIs, because of their role in providing data and services to monitor the wellness and security of planet Earth environment.

In general, the engagement of stakeholders requires the formulation and delivery of communication policies and interaction strategies that are appropriate to the diverse target audiences. In particular, for the engagement of the Private Sector, these strategies and policies must be designed having a timeline compliant with the RI development. EPOS adopted the strategy of "*informing it*" during the Preparatory Phase and "*consulting it*" during the Implementation Phase. To proceed on this path, EPOS launched a consultation to map the landscape of interactions with the private sector within the EPOS communities. Indeed, the Private sector is already engaged in many EPOS activities as users, suppliers and/or customers of thematic services (e.g., seismic hazard and risk, anthropogenic hazard, multi-scale laboratories). Moreover, EPOS is providing access to data products obtained from restricted data provided by industry (e.g., mining industry) and is developing the provision of new scientific products and services to a wide community of users. This engagement, however, presently is mostly in the form of bilateral collaborations between scientists and the private sector. The main goal of the above-mentioned survey is actually to assess the impact of such interactions on EPOS data and service provision and to plan future engagement strategies. EPOS is well aware that it requires time and efforts to convince the Private Sector to be engaged within a pan-European multi-lateral framework. The outcome of the survey is reported in details in Annex 2.

2.4 Stakeholder Category: Society

As described in the EPOS IP Communication Plan (D2.1), the interaction with society is mainly demanded to the EPOS communication tools, as the Website (www.epos-ip.org) and social media (Facebook; Twitter; LinkedIn, etc.). At this stage, these tools are the most efficient contributor to keep informed Society about EPOS.

The website, regularly updated, is fully active since December 2015 (M3). The design of the website has been streamlined to promote usability and engagement.

The website contains all information about the organization, goals, activities of EPOS initiative and EPOS IP project. The home page, in particular, contains information about EPOS (Introducing EPOS information and video); presents the current news and events; gives links to the EPOS thematic core services web-pages; presents Twitter feeds and gives access to the EPOS official YouTube Channel and other social media

The EPOS IP approach for selecting suitable "social channels" has considered the popularity of the platform, the typology of end-users, the level of engagement and continuity required for the specific platform. EPOS main social channels and their links to get access are the following:

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/EPOS-European-Plate-Observing-System-155473037830465/>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/EPOSeu>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/epos-european-plate-observing-system-63a85412a/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/user/eposeu>

Flickr: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/eposeu/>

EPOS communication team organized and scheduled weekly plans of posts, creating automatic procedures on directly reposting news from the website.

In general, the interaction and the communication with society at large, are expected to increase in the last year of the EPOS Implementation phase, when demonstrators and services will be validated to enter in the pre-operational and testing phase. The availability of new products and services targeted to society will be part of the validation and testing procedure.

Annex 1 - EPOS Info-Day Ljubljana

The EPOS IP project, in the framework of its Communication and Dissemination activities, organized an EPOS Brokerage event in Ljubljana, Slovenia on the 29 - 30 May 2018.

The event called “EPOS Info-Day”, and it was organised by ZRC SAZU, Slovenia, the local co-organizer; IGF PAS, Poland; INGV, Italy (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – The EPOS INFO-DAY flyer.

This initiative, scheduled in the EPOS Communication Plan, was dedicated to disseminate, inform, engage and eventually involve potential users and stakeholders of the EPOS infrastructure and its integration plan.

The EPOS Info-Day was an opportunity to present the global perspectives of the EPOS pan-European infrastructure and to highlight its impact for solid-Earth science.

The event was targeted to potential users and stakeholders from the Eastern Adriatic area: scientists from research organizations and universities, policy-makers, and other people interested in learning about EPOS, its provision in terms of scientific data, products and services as well as to foster interregional and international cooperation in an enlarged Europe, across its borders.

On the 29th afternoon, the Info-Day focused on the strategic implications of participating in the EPOS integration plan and to the construction of the new EPOS research infrastructure. On the 30th morning, the scientific and technological impact was discussed, with a particular focus on scientific data and service provision. Contributions from several Thematic Core Services (Seismology, GNSS Data & Products, Geomagnetic Observations, and Geological Information and Modelling) were scheduled in the agenda, together with open discussions to foster effective and open exchanges of ideas.

The event welcomed 52 participants from 14 countries (Figure 4), 5 of them (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Kosovo, Rep. of Macedonia, Montenegro), currently not part of EPOS.

Figure 4 - Participants at EPOS INFO-DAY in Ljubljana.

Beside five members of local co-organizer ZRC SAZU (Slovenia), there were 15 additional participants from EPOS-Slovenia community. This was a first-hand opportunity to get information about state of the art and future development of EPOS, especially related to TCS-Seismology, TCS-GNSS Data & Products, TCS-Geomagnetic Observations, and TCS-Geological Information and Modeling.

There were, also, 5 participants from the University of Trieste and OGS (Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale) who met potential partners for future scientific cooperation.

TCS leaders Florian Haslinger (seismology), Pavel Hejda (Geomagnetic Observations), François Robida (Geological Information and Modelling), TCS leader-proxy Rui Cardoso and David Zuliani (GNSS Data & Products) and Grzegorz Lizurek (TCS-Anthropogenic hazard data and services) gave precise talks how each EPOS Research Infrastructure works. Irene Molinari (ETH, Switzerland) presented AlpArray project.

Lilli Freda, EPOS IP Project Director, presented the vision and mission of the EPOS project. Massimo Cocco, the Project Coordinator, gave talks on architecture and implementation phase of EPOS, EPOS-ERIC, and harmonization with national strategies and priorities.

Keith Jeffery presented ICS: a novel approach to support FAIR data principles and scientific research and connected with Daniele Bailo (INGV) and Wayne Shelley to present Live demonstrator #EPOS_ICS future infrastructure for EPOS web services platform.

The event was followed on https://twitter.com/EPOS_Slovenia. The Info-Day agenda is represented in Figure 5.

In the evening of 29th May 2018, a visit in Ljubljana downtown related to signs of 1895 earthquake was led by the mag. Ina Cecić (President of European Seismological Commission, Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning, Seismology office). A not official walk after the rainy day in the hotel's lecture room and stand-up dinner gave participants even more opportunities to exchange ideas.

Figure 5 - The EPOS INFO-DAY Agenda.

Annex 2 – Report on Consultation with Private Sector

CONSULTATION ON COOPERATION BETWEEN PRIVATE SECTOR AND THE EPOS TCSs’ COMMUNITIES

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUMMARY.....	17
BACKGROUND	17
THE CONSULTATION.....	17
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONTRIBUTIONS	19
EPOS TCSs communities’ cooperation with the Private Sector	19
Type of Cooperation.....	19
The institutional framework of collaboration.....	20
The financial framework of collaboration.....	21
Existing or potential target audience	22
Strategic plan to manage ethics issues	23
Data Policy & Access Rules	23
Past and future cooperation with the Private Sector.....	24
CONSIDERATIONS	25
ANNEX 1 - FORM A) THE RESPONDENT REPRESENTS AN EPOS IP BENEFICIARY/PARTNER.....	26
ANNEX 2 - FORM B) THE RESPONDENT REPRESENTS A EPOS TCS COMMUNITY.....	29
ANNEX 3	33

Summary

To reach the goal of maximum exploitation in terms of both, a large volume of used services and a large number of users, EPOS interacts with and engages very different stakeholders, including scientists belonging to disciplines outside the solid Earth domain as well as decision-makers, the private sector and the society.

The consultation on cooperation with private sector intended to map the landscape of interactions with private sector within the EPOS communities. The goal was to assess the impact of such interactions on EPOS data and service provision and to plan forthcoming engagement strategies.

Background

The private sector represents one of the EPOS stakeholders' categories (here disaggregated into Large Industries and Small and medium-sized enterprises target audiences) that must be engaged for a wide-ranging and effective exploitation of the EPOS achievements. An effective engagement of the private sector also strongly contributes ensuring the Socio-Economic Impact (SEI) is realised. However, cooperation with the private sector is a challenge for publicly funded RIs, such as EPOS that must retain impartiality and public-good role. Moreover, cooperation with the private sector must manage in parallel with scientific, financial, legal, governance and ethics issues. The latter are especially pertinent for environmental RIs, because of their role in providing data and services to monitor the wellness and security of the planet Earth environment.

The engagement of stakeholders requires, in general, the formulation and delivery of communication policies and interaction strategies that are appropriate to the diverse target audiences. In particular, for the private sector engagement these strategies and policies must be designed having a timeline compliant with the RI development. For the category Private Sector, EPOS adopted the strategy of "*informing it*" during the Preparatory Phase and "*engaging it*" during the Implementation Phase.

The consultation

Questions have been addressed to two types of respondents:

1. The project partners
2. The Work Package leaders in collaboration with the TCS Communication contact Persons

Accordingly, two different forms have been elaborated:

- **Form A:** addressed to a respondent representing the EPOS IP Partner (Annex 1)
- **Form B:** addressed to a respondent representing the TCS community (Annex 2)

"Respondents 1", have been instructed to answer as many sections as possible considering that the more information they could made available, the greater the opportunity for planning the EPOS engagement strategy.

"Respondents 2" have been asked to collect the answer of "respondents 1" and to elaborate them in a unique form, reflecting the overview of the community's collaboration with the Private Sector. The Consultation has been launched on November the 30th, and it was addressed to TCSs WP Leaders. On December the 9th also TCS Communication Contact Persons have been involved and asked to collaborate.

The TCS WP Leaders and the TCSs CCPs then contacted their Community to collect answers and provide a significant sample of them.

The deadline to collect answers has been fixed at the end of December 2016.

The answers have been treated in the utmost confidence and only the EPOS Project Management Office (PMO) has reviewed them. All data have been stored safely and used only in a merged form.

Statistical analysis of the contributions

EPOS TCSs communities' cooperation with the Private Sector

Over 10 TCSs Communities, 80% of the partner organisations participating in the consultation declared their cooperation with large industries (Figure 1), and 70% of them detailed their collaboration with Small and medium-sized enterprises SMEs (Figure 2).

Figure 1

EPOS TCSs communities' cooperation with large industries

Figure 2

EPOS TCSs communities' cooperation with SMEs

Type of Cooperation

Regarding the type of cooperation existing (question 1b) between the partner organizations and the private sector, considering the Private Sector as a supplier, a user or a customer (Annex 3) of the Research Infrastructure (RI), it resulted that the three types of relation are almost equally represented (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3

Figure 4

The institutional framework of collaboration

In terms of framework of collaboration (question 1c), in general the cooperation is mainly taking place within (Figure 5 and Figure 6):

- An institutional collaborative framework
- Other frameworks of collaboration

The respondents have also identified other frameworks of collaboration:

- Private (i.e. service contracts, and informal agreements; direct appointments)
- International framework of collaboration (i.e. International networks and agencies e.g. EUREF and ISS; European framework of collaboration).

Figure 5

Figure 6

The financial framework of collaboration

In relation to the financial framework (question 1d), it appears that in collaborating with the large industry, the private funds are the main financing scheme, followed by the Nationals funds for Research (Figure 7).

Instead, when the focus moves to the cooperation with the SMEs (Figure 8), the situation is more equally distributed between the Nationals funds for Research and Economic Development and other kind of financial schemes (i.e. the private, the European and the international ones).

Figure 7

Figure 8

Existing or potential target audience

In terms of existing and potential target audience in the private sector, including both categories, the large industries and the SMEs, the consultation shows (Figure 9) that the three main target sectors are the Geo-Energy, the Geo-Resources and the Technological Development & Innovation.

Also other sectors have been identified. They are:

- Tourist companies
- Hazards Consultants
- Geotechnical firms
- Groundwater engineering firms
- Environmental consultants
- Drilling contractors
- Environmental remediation
- Pollution
- Human Health
- Geo-hazards

- Global positioning

Figure 9

Strategic plan to manage ethics issues

Based on the enquiry, the ethical issues while cooperating with private sector (large industries and SMEs) are usually managed individually by each institution, *in bilateral agreement*, according to national legislation.

Data Policy & Access Rules

Not all the TCSs have specifically addressed the issues related to “Data Policy and Access Rules for users”. In general, it is possible to state that data and products are generally open access (Figure 10 and Figure 11).

Figure 10

Figure 11

Past and future cooperation with the Private Sector

Past and future cooperation with the private sector is clearly demonstrated by the feedback received (Figure 12 and Figure 13). Also, it is possible to state that in terms of data or service provision within EU Programmes, 5 TCSs are involved in (e.g. Copernicus).

Figure 12

Figure 13

Considerations

The interaction between Private Sector and the EPOS Communities is certainly well structured and strong. Nevertheless, further actions will be unquestionably undertaken, including the launch of a new consultation that, on the bases of the feedback received, will have the intention to deeper analyse this cooperation.

Also, EPOS TCS communities will organize and participate in targeted activities focused on the engagement of this specific stakeholder’s category, as for examples brokerage events. The objectives of this kind of events will be to present EPOS, its data and service provision, the TCSs Communities and to prepare future co-operations between participants. These will have the opportunity to present themselves and to meet representatives from companies and SMEs, in order to paving the way for future co-operations.

ANNEX 1 - Form A) the respondent represents an EPOS IP Beneficiary/Partner
General Information on the respondent

- Name of the respondent:
- Name of the institution:
- Country:

1. Please describe ongoing experience of cooperation with private sector (PS), only for sector/s relevant for EPOS. (if you are cooperating with more than one enterprise, please describe the enterprises separately by duplicating this form)		
1a)	Describe the type of enterprise	<input type="radio"/> Large Industry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Name..... ▪ Field of interests/actions <input type="radio"/> Small/Medium Enterprise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Name ▪ Field of interests/actions
1b)	Describe the type of cooperation (See Annex 1 for details)	<input type="radio"/> PS as Suppliers of RIs <input type="radio"/> PS as Users of RIs <input type="radio"/> PS as Customers of RIs
1c)	Describe the institutional framework of the collaboration	<input type="radio"/> Through a national governmental commitment <input type="radio"/> Through a regional governmental commitment <input type="radio"/> Within an institutional collaborative framework <input type="radio"/> Other, please specify
1d)	Describe the financial framework of the collaboration	<input type="radio"/> National funds for Economic Development <input type="radio"/> National funds for Research <input type="radio"/> Structural funds <input type="radio"/> Private funds <input type="radio"/> Other, please specify
2. Please list existing or potential target audience in the PS		
<input type="radio"/> Geo-Energy <input type="radio"/> Geo-Resources <input type="radio"/> Aviation <input type="radio"/> Re-insurance / insurance <input type="radio"/> Technological development & innovation <input type="radio"/> Global Positioning		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> IT service providers (including HPC, HTC) <input type="radio"/> Others, please list
3. Type/Class of data, products, services and/or facilities involved in the cooperation with PS	
Detail the above described cooperation activities in terms of type/class of data, products, services and/or facilities	
4. Contributions included in the EPOS provision	
Among info provided in section 3, please list those type/class of data, products, services and/or facilities included in the EPOS provision	
5. Management of Ethics Issues	
Do you have any strategy or plan to manage Ethics issues (e.g. data security, risk communication to society, users security, malevolent use of data, ...)	
6. Data Policy & Access Rules	
Are you, as institution, adopting a data policy and access rules for users?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> NO we are not adopting data policy and access rules <input type="radio"/> YES we are adopting a data policy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes data/products are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Open Access <input type="radio"/> Embargoed <input type="radio"/> Restricted <input type="radio"/> Yes Services are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Open Access <input type="radio"/> Embargoed <input type="radio"/> Restricted <input type="radio"/> Yes Software is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Open Access <input type="radio"/> Embargoed <input type="radio"/> Restricted <input type="radio"/> YES we are adopting access rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes Access can be (multiple answers):

		<input type="radio"/> Anonymous <input type="radio"/> Registered <input type="radio"/> Authorized <input type="radio"/> Other Comments, please specify
7. Service provision to industry in European programs		
	Are you involved in data or service provision within European programs (e.g. Copernicus). Please specify.	
8. Future cooperation with PS		
	Briefly describe cooperation strategies	
9. Past cooperation with PS		
	List your past cooperation with PS (simply a list of companies)	

ANNEX 2 - Form B) the respondent represents a EPOS TCS community**General Information on the respondent**

- Name of the respondent:
- Name of the community (or EPOS IP TCS WP):

LARGE INDUSTRIES**1. Please describe ongoing experience of cooperation with private sector (PS) in your community.****1a) Names and field of interest**

List of large industries for the TCSX:

-
-
-

TCSX cooperates with the large industries in the following sectors:

-
-
-

1b) Type of cooperation

Cooperation with the above listed large industries can be in the type of PS being

1c) Institutional framework of the collaboration

Collaboration with large industries and TCSX partners take places in a collaborative framework.

1d) Financial framework of the collaboration

The financial framework for collaboration between large industries in the PS and the partners of the TCSX is

2. Please list existing or potential target audience in the PS

-
-
-

3. Type/Class of data, products, services and/or facilities involved in the cooperation with PS

The type of data, products and services involved in the cooperation with PS

4. Contributions included in the EPOS provision

Among info provided in section 3, the following type/class of data, products, services and/or facilities were listed as included in the EPOS provision:

-
-

-
-

5. Management of Ethics Issues

The ethical issues during cooperating with private companies and factories are usually managed in

6. Data Policy & Access Rules

The access to the data/products is

7. Service provision to industry in European programs

Services provided to the PS in European programs are

8. Future co-operation with PS

Future cooperation between TCSX partners and large industries in the PS

9. Past cooperation with PS

Past cooperation between TCSX partners and large industries in the PS

SMALL / MEDIUM ENTERPRISE**1. Please describe ongoing experience of cooperation with private sector (PS) in your community.****1a) Names and field of interest**

List of large industries for the TCSX:

-
-
-

TCSX cooperates with the large industries in the following sectors:

-
-
-

1b) Type of cooperation

Cooperation with the above listed large industries can be in the type of PS being

1c) Institutional framework of the collaboration

Collaboration with large industries and TCSX partners take places in a collaborative framework.

1d) Financial framework of the collaboration

The financial framework for collaboration between large industries in the PS and the partners of the TCSX is

2. Please list existing or potential target audience in the PS

-
-
-

3. Type/Class of data, products, services and/or facilities involved in the cooperation with PS

The type of data, products and services involved in the cooperation with PS

4. Contributions included in the EPOS provision

Among info provided in section 3, the following type/class of data, products, services and/or facilities were listed as included in the EPOS provision:

-
-
-

5. Management of Ethics Issues

The ethical issues during cooperating with private companies and factories are usually managed in

6. Data Policy & Access Rules

The access to the data/products is

7. Service provision to industry in European programs

Services provided to the PS in European programs are

8. Future co-operation with PS

Future cooperation between TCSX partners and large industries in the PS

9. Past cooperation with PS

Past cooperation between TCSX partners and large industries in the PS

ANNEX 3

PS as a supplier. Both Large Industry and SMEs can act as suppliers to RIs. They may supply raw data or data products, potentially accessible through the infrastructure; they may collaborate developing technology for building RI elements (sensors, experimental apparatuses, digital acquisition systems) and they can also provide access to their facilities. Nevertheless, the integration at Pan-European level of public data collected by national RIs with data generated by Large Industry and SMEs is not always possible for environmental sciences for different reasons. In the following, we list those concerning EPOS:

- i. The lack of shared, open access policies for most of the geophysical data collected by industry (such as for geo-resources and anthropogenic hazards).
- ii. The limited possibility to commercialize data products and RI elements in a competitive market.
- iii. The conflict between the regional/national interests of the industry and the Pan-European dimension and perspective of EPOS (25 participating countries, 256 multidisciplinary RIs representing different communities, 138 national public research institutions providing access to a wealth of available data collected by existing RIs): that is, bilateral against multilateral collaborative framework and policies.
- iv. The need to harmonize the EPOS implementation plans with national priorities since the involved RIs exist and are often operating for the geo-monitoring of the national territory (public role for society).

PS as a user. More frequently, large industries and SMEs will be users of RI data, products, services or facilities (e.g. experimental facilities, testing innovative developments and products). This requires decisions on pricing structures for commercial use of data and products, and the adoption of a data policy allowing commercial use of data.

PS as a customer. The PS can be a customer of a public RI, because of its interest in innovative services that can be developed through public scientific infrastructures involving both investments and human capital. In this case, there is a co-investment by beneficiaries, i.e. private and public, being customers and users at the same time and both benefitting from the outcomes.